

REVIEW

Ontology-based resilient and sustainable resource allocation and scheduling in healthcare systems: a review

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ARTICLE HISTORY

Compiled June 28, 2026

Table 1. Other commonly used indices for health equity calculation

Name	Formula	Features
Regression and Correlation Analysis (RCA) (truelove1993measurement ; roeger2010equity)	$\sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)^2}$ <p>where Y is the observed variable while \hat{Y} is the estimated variable from a regression</p>	Suitable when there is a clear connection between variables under the interests, such as available resources, and needs such as population.
Spatial Autocorrelation (SpA) (smoyer2004spatial ; bowen1995toward)	$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij} (Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)(Y_j - \hat{Y}_j)}{\sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)^2 \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij}}$ <p>where Y is the observed variable while \hat{Y} is the estimated variable from a regression, w is the spatial weights matrix which depends on the influence between two groups.</p>	Suitable for spatial equity problems which influence between groups under investigation can be observed. For example, if two areas have a shared border or not.
Concentration Index (CI) (witthayapipopsakul2019equity ; wagstaff2007analyzing ; gan2015equitable)	$\frac{2}{N\mu} \sum_{i=1}^n h_i r_i - 1 - \frac{1}{N}$ <p>where h_i is the resource related variable, μ is its mean, and $r_i = i/N$ is the fractional rank of individual i in the living standards distribution, with $i = 1$ for the poorest and $i = N$ for the richest</p>	Depends only on the relationship between the resource variable and the rank of the need related factors and not on the value of the factors themselves.
Corrected Concentration Index (CCI) (bonfrer2014does)	$4 \left[\sum_{k=1}^K \beta_k \bar{x}_k CI(x_k) + \sum_{j=1}^J \beta_j \bar{z}_j CI(z_j) + GC_\epsilon \right]$ <p>with \bar{x} and \bar{z} representing the means of x, need related variable, and z non-need related variable, respectively, and $CI(x)$ and $CI(z)$ are their concentration indices, GC_ϵ is a residual term.</p>	Suitable for a mix of need related variables and non-need related ones. Can be used with correlation analysis to identify the underlying drivers of inequity.
Atkinson Index (AtI) (de2007income ; sitthiyot2020simple)	$1 - \left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{y_i}{\bar{y}} \right)^{1-\epsilon} \right)^{\frac{1}{1-\epsilon}}, \epsilon \neq 1$ $1 - \frac{\prod_{i=1}^N \left(y_i^{\frac{1}{N}} \right)}{\bar{y}}, \epsilon = 1$ <p>where y_i denotes the individual variable, \bar{y} denotes the average, N is the number of populations or groups, and ϵ is a sensitivity coefficient.</p>	Has a sensitivity coefficient (ϵ) that varies in the weight given to inequity in different groups. As ϵ increases, more concern is given to the lower end of the health resource distribution. In practice, ϵ values of 0.5, 1, 1.5 or 2 are used.
Generalized Entropy (GE) index (mussard2003decomposition ; dagum1997decomposition)	$\frac{1}{\alpha(\alpha-1)} \left[\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{y_i}{\bar{y}} \right)^\alpha - 1 \right]$ <p>where y_i denotes the individual variable, \bar{y} denotes the average, N is the number of populations or groups, and α is a sensitivity coefficient.</p>	Has a sensitivity coefficient (α) that varies in the weight given to inequity in different groups. The more positive α (typically $-1, 0, 1$ or 2) is, the more sensitive $GE(\alpha)$ is to inequity at the top of the resource distribution.
Robbin Hood Index (RH) (sohler2003income ; omrani2013equity)	$\frac{1}{2} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N x_i - \bar{x} }{\sum_{i=1}^N x_i}$ <p>where x_i denotes the individual variable, \bar{x} denotes the average.</p>	Does not require a sensitivity coefficient. It measures the maximum vertical distance from the Lorenz curve to the 45° line of equity